

Annamalai's Binomial Expansion

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Abstract: Nowadays, the growing complexity of mathematical and computational modelling demands the simplicity of mathematical and combinatorial equations for solving today's scientific problems and challenges. This paper presents a novel binomial expansion. This idea can enable the scientific researchers to solve the real life problems.

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Novel Binomial Expansion

The novel binomial expansion or binomial theorem given below is constituted using the binomial coefficients defined in combinatorial geometrics [1, 2].

Annamalai's Binomial Theorem:
$$\sum_{i=0}^r V_i^{r+1} = \sum_{i=0}^r (r+1-i)V_i^r.$$

Proof. Let us use the theorem given in the journal paper entitled 'Annamalai's binomial identity and theorem [1] to prove this novel binomial expansion.

$$\sum_{i=0}^n V_i^{r+1} x^i = \sum_{i=0}^n V_i^r x^i + \sum_{i=1}^n V_{i-1}^r x^i + \sum_{i=2}^n V_{i-2}^r x^i + \cdots + \sum_{i=n-1}^n V_{i-(n-1)}^r x^i + \sum_{i=n}^n V_{i-n}^r x^i. \quad (1)$$

By substituting $n = r$ and $x = 1$ in the equation (1), we get

$$\sum_{i=0}^r V_i^{r+1} x^i = \sum_{i=0}^r V_i^r + \sum_{i=1}^r V_{i-1}^r + \sum_{i=2}^r V_{i-2}^r + \cdots + \sum_{i=r-1}^r V_{i-(r-1)}^r + \sum_{i=r}^r V_{i-r}^r. \quad (2)$$

Let us expand the summations on right hand side given in the equation (2).

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{i=0}^r V_i^r + \sum_{i=1}^r V_{i-1}^r + \sum_{i=2}^r V_{i-2}^r + \cdots + \sum_{i=r-1}^r V_{i-(r-1)}^r + \sum_{i=r}^r V_{i-r}^r \\ &= (V_0^r + V_1^r + V_2^r + V_3^r + \cdots + V_r^r) + (V_0^r + V_1^r + V_2^r + V_3^r + \cdots + V_{r-1}^r) \\ & \quad + (V_0^r + V_1^r + V_2^r + V_3^r + \cdots + V_{r-2}^r) + \cdots + (V_0^r + V_1^r) + V_0^r. \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

In the equation (3), the number of terms $V_0^r, V_1^r, V_2^r, V_3^r, \dots, V_{r-2}^r, V_{r-1}^r,$ and V_r^r are $(r+1), r, (r-1), (r-2), \dots, 3, 2,$ and 1 respectively. Now, we can conclude that

$$\sum_{i=0}^r V_i^{r+1} = (r+1)V_0^r + rV_1^r + (r-1)V_2^r + \cdots + 3V_{(r-2)}^r + 2V_{(r-1)}^r + V_r^r.$$

$$\therefore \sum_{i=0}^r V_i^{r+1} = \sum_{i=0}^r (r+1-i)V_i^r.$$

Corollary:
$$\sum_{i=0}^n V_i^{r+1} = \sum_{i=0}^n (n+1-i)V_i^r.$$

References

- [1] Annamalai, C. (2022) Annamalai's Binomial Identity and Theorem, *SSRN Electronic Journal*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4097907>.
- [2] Annamalai, C. (2022) Algorithmic Approach for Computation of Binomial Expansions, *OSF Preprints*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/a9cwh>.